

No. 7—BHOPAL BIRLA MUSEUM INSCRIPTION OF THE TIME OF JAYASIMHADĒVA II, VIKRAMA 1308

(1 Plate)

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The inscription, edited below with the kind permission of the Director (Epigraphy), Archaeological Survey of India, Mysore, is engraved on a stone pillar now kept in the Birla Museum, Bhopal. According to the museum authorities, the pillar was originally found in the village Bamai in Raisen District in Madhya Pradesh. During my visit to Bhopal in March 1979, the museum officials were good enough to permit me to examine the inscription and prepare estampages for which I am thankful to them.¹

The inscribed area measures about 25 cm in length and 27.4 cm in breadth. The size of the letters is not uniform and varies in height from 1.4 cm to 2.2 cm. The **characters** are Nāgarī and they are regular for the period to which the record belongs. Among the **palaeographical** features, the following are noteworthy. Both the forms of medial sign for ē occur here; one of them is indicated by a *prishthamātrā* as found in *varshē* in line 1, *gramē* in line 4, etc. The other is denoted by a *śīromātrā* as seen in *Vudhē* in line 1, *dēva* in line 14, etc. There are in all 14 lines of writing. The **language** of the record is Sanskrit influenced by local dialect as seen in the use of such words as *kārāpyā*, *lagna* in line 6. The inscription is partly in prose and partly in verse. As regards **orthography**, the following features are noteworthy 1) The use of *v* for *b* as noticed in words like *Vudhē* in line 1 and *vrāhmaṇa* in line 8; 2) the doubling of consonants immediately preceded by *r* as for instance in words like *dharmma* in line 7, *sarvvā* in line 12 and *nirmmalah* in line 13.

The inscription commences with the auspicious word *ōm* expressed by a partly damaged symbol. This is followed by the details of the date, viz., Vikrama 1308, Āśvina vadi 12, Wednesday corresponding to 1251 A.D., September 13, f.d.t. °23, the month being *Pūrṇimānta*. The record then refers itself to the reign of the king Jayasimhadēva. It mentions also his chief minister (*mahāpradhāna*) *Rāja Kāmadēva*. Thereafter, it records that a temple (*āyatana*) of Talakēśvara was caused to be built by *Rāja Talakasimha*, the son of *Rāja Salakhē* at the village of *Vrā(Brā)hma*. It is further stated that a sum of 400 *drammas* were spent probably by Talakasimha, in connection with the *udyāpana* ceremony conducted very likely on the completion of the construction of the temple of Talakēśvara. The word *lagna* used in the nominative case here generally means 'adhered, clinging' etc.² In the present context, however, it may probably mean 'connected with, pertaining to' leading to the conclusion that the ceremony in question involved an expenditure of 400 *drammas*. The performance of *udyāpana* ceremony on the completion of any structure is well known in this period and this has been referred to in another inscription of the same king from Paṭhāri, dated Vikrama 1326.³ In the verse portion that follows Talakasimha's father, his wife and

1 This has been noticed in *A.R.Ep.*, 1978-79, under Appendix B 195.

2 *Sanskrit-Hindi-English Dictionary* by Suryakanta, p 496.

3 Above, Vol. XXXVIII, pp. 33 ff.

his brother are described. Verse 1 mentions Talakasimha and his father Salakhē.¹ Talakasimha was well-known as *dharmasīla* and he was even devoted to the gods and the *brāhmaṇas*. Verse 2 describes his wife Goga as of good character (*śilini*) and as the very incarnation of intelligence (*mati-rūpini*). She was very much devoted to her husband. The verse ends with a wish for the growth of her fame (*kirtti*). Verse 3 describes Talakasimha's brother by name Nāmadeva. He was always devoted to his studies and was a valiant and chaste person. It is not clear from the epigraph what Nāmadeva did to warrant his mention therein.² This (i.e., the text of the inscription) was narrated (probably composed) by *pañ*^o Mahāśarman and engraved (*utkirna*) by *sutradhāra* Ubhayadēva, the son of Sahadēva.

The epigraph under study is important in as much as this is the earliest inscription discovered so far of Jayasimhadēva who is no doubt identical with Jayasimhadēva II—Jayavarman II of the Paramāra family, who ruled over the Malwa region during the period in question and is already known to us from a number of inscriptions.³

With the discovery of the present epigraph, the accession of Jayavarman II is pre-dated to 1251 A.D., as against 1255 A.D. hitherto known to us.⁴ The name of *Mahāpradhāna* Kāmadeva is made available to us for the first time in this inscription. It is quite probable that he was the *mahāpradhāna* of Jayasimhadēva—Jayavarman II in the early part of his reign for in Vikrama 1317 (1260 A.D.), Rājā Ajayadēva figures as the king's *mahāpradhāna*.⁵

The village Vra (Bra)hma, where the temple of Talakēśvara (the god evidently so named after the donor) was constructed, is obviously identical with the modern village Bamai in Raisen District where the inscription was originally discovered.

TEXT⁶

[Metre : Verses 1-3 *Anuṣṭubh*]

1. Ōm⁷ [!*] saṃvatu(t) 1308 varshe Āśvina vadi 2 Vu(bu)dhe ady=e-
- 2 ha samasta-rajavali-virajita-śrīmajj]=Jayasimha-
- 3 dēva-vijayarajye mahāpradhāna-raja-śrī-Kāmadē-

- 1 Salakhanasimha figures as the father of the donor Anayasimha in the Māndhātā plates of the same king, dated Vikrama 1331 (Above, Vol XXXII, pp 139 ff) Could he be identical with Salakhe, father of the donor Talakasimha of the present epigraph in which case Anayasimha and Talakasimha will have to be deemed as brothers born to Salakha This will make Nāmadeva, mentioned in the record under study, as another son of Salakhanasimha *alias* Salakhē
- 2 In this context the reference to Talakasimha as *varggin* in verse 1 is of interest The word actually means 'devoted' to a side or a party or a family Talakasimha was obviously greatly attached to the members of his family and this may explain why the inscription contains references to his father Salakha, wife Gogā and brother Nāmadeva none of whom was directly involved with the object of the inscription
- 3 Rāhatgarh stone inscription, *Ind Ant.*, Vol XX, p 84, Mōdi stone inscription, *PRAS W C.*, 1912-13, p 56, *A R Ep.*, 1950-51, B 124, Māndhātā Copper-plate grant, above, Vol IX, pp 117 ff. Bhilsa stone inscription, *ibid.*, Vol XXXV, p 187. Paṭhāri stone inscription, *ibid.*, Vol XXXVIII, pp 33 ff., Māndhātā Copper-plate grant, *ibid.*, Vol XXXII, pp 139 ff
- 4 *Contra. The Paramāras* (by P Bhatia), p 154
- 5 Above, Vol IX, p 119
- 6 From inked impressions
- 7 Expressed by a partly preserved symbol

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 JAYASIMHADĒVA II, VIKRAMA 1308

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- 4 va-samayē adya Vṛā(Bṛā)hma-grāmē rāja-śrī-Salakhē-suta-
 5 rāja-Talakasīrha¹dēva² śrī-Talakēśvaraḥ sa³ āya-
 6 tanam kārāpyām ⁴|| sa⁵ udyāpanē lagna-dramā[h*] 400 ||
 7 Dharmmaśīl=iti vikhyātaḥ rāja-śrī- Salakhē- su-
 8 taḥ | dēva-vṛā(brā)hmaṇa-parō nityam⁶ Talakasīr[ha*]sya va-
 9 rggīṇaḥ [||1||] Tasya bhāryā tu Gōga yā śīlini ma-
 10 ti-rūpiṇi | ativa-bhartri(rṭri)-bhaktā cha tasyāḥ kīrtis=tu va-
 11 rddhatu [||*] 2 [||*] Talakasīrhasya bhā(bhrā)tur-yaḥ Nāmadēv-ē-
 12 ti viśrutaḥ || (I) sarvv-ābhyāsa-parō nityam paurush-ā[t]i-
 13 khyāti-nirmmalah⁶ [||3||] uktam=idam Paṁ° śrī-Mahā-śarmē(rma)-
 14 ṇa(ṇā) || Sūtradhārah⁷ Sahadēva-suta-Ubhayadēv[e]na utki-
 15 [rṇṇam*] [||*]

1 There is a scratch after the letter *ha*, looking like a *visarga* mark.

2 Read *odēvena*.

3 Read *Talakēśvarasya*.

4 Read *kāritam* or *kārāpitam*.

5 Read *tasya*.

6 This quarter is metrically defective, there being 9 syllables instead of 8.

7 Read *sūtradhāreṇa*.

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